

Miscellanea Araneologica

2022

Manchester, UK

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On the taxonomic rank of the major subdivisions of the extant segmented spiders (Arachnida : Araneae : Mesothelae : Liphistiidae s. lat.)

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Abstract. The extant primitively segmented spiders of the family Liphistiidae s. lat. are a monophyletic, morphologically and ecologically conservative group of “living fossils” that have undergone a surprisingly recent radiation in their small contiguous range in Southeast Asia. Splitting the family into two separate families, Liphistiidae s. str. and Heptathelidae, is not justified and would obscure the most important evolutionary features of the group.

The extant representative of the Mesothelae or primitively segmented spiders have long been recognised as a monophyletic group and classified in a single family Liphistiidae Thorell, 1869, by most authors (Raven 1985, Jocqué & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006, Xu et al. 2015a,b, Xu et al, 2021). The group contains two distinct major lineages, which have usually been considered subfamilies, Liphistiinae and Heptathelinae Kishida, 1923. Just like the monophyly of the Liphistiidae, the monophyly of its two subfamilies has never been seriously contested, and they have some sometimes even been elevated to family rank (e.g., Petrunkevitch 1939, Haupt 1983, 2003, Wunderlich 2017). However, such proposals of splitting the Liphistiidae s. lat. never found general acceptance, given the overall homogeneity of the family (Bristowe [1976] writes that he “doubt[s] whether even generic rank is justified. *Heptathela* is remarkably similar to *Liphistius* in all other respects [except the configuration of the spinnerets]”).

Recently, Li (2022) once again proposed the elevation of Liphistiinae and Heptathelinae to family rank. In his short note of less than two pages, he does not provide a single argument to support this split, not even a single word to attempt to justify his proposal. Instead, in lieu of a scientific motivation, he simply refers to two

earlier publications on the phylogeny of Liphistiidae (Xu et al. 2015a, 2021). These two publications confirm the monophyly of Liphistiidae s. lat., as well as that of its two subfamilies. They do not discuss a change in the rank of the subfamilies, and do not present any evidence for or against such a splitting of the family. Nevertheless, the World Spider Catalog (<http://wsc.nmbe.ch>), which acts as the self-appointed arbiter on taxonomic controversies in araneology and had refused to implement the same change when it was proposed previously, e.g., by Haupt (2003) and Wunderlich (2017), accepted Li’s unexplained decision immediately and without discussion.

The rank of taxonomic divisions above the species level is often subjective, but it should not be arbitrary – decisions to split (or merge) taxa at this level require even more tact and discretion than the more objective decisions at the species level, if we are to avoid a descent into taxonomic anarchy (see Giribet et al. [2016] for a detailed discussion of the subjectivity of Linnaean ranks and its implications, and Kallal et al. [2020] for an application in araneology). Such destabilising decisions need particularly good scientific support in a case like this, where the species involved are without exception of conservation concern, as a result of their longevity, poor dispersal capacity and very restricted distribution. It is, therefore, worthwhile to examine this case in a bit more detail.

The extant Mesothelae, Liphistiidae s. lat., are morphologically and ecologically a very conservative and homogenous group, often described as “living fossils” among spiders (Xu et al., 2015b). Their distribution is restricted to a relatively small, contiguous area in Southeast Asia, where they have undergone a recent local diversification, while maintaining their overall archaic morphology and behaviour, including numerous plesiomorphic characters lost in all other spiders (Haupt 2003). While Liphistiidae s. lat. are easily recognised as a very distinct group, dramatically different from all other extant spiders, the differences within the family are relatively subtle. Splitting it into multiple separate families would require a very strong argument in its favour.

One such argument could be that Liphistiidae s. lat. are a polyphyletic group. However, there is no evidence to support such an assertion. All authors agree on the monophyly of Liphistiidae s. lat. among recent spiders, beginning with the first cladistic analysis of the question by Platnick & Gertsch (1976) and supported by all later analyses, based on molecular or morphological data (e.g., Raven 1985, Haupt 2003, Xu et al. 2015b). The compact geographical distribution and the parapatric relationship between the two extant subfamilies supports the hypothesis that they also form a monophyletic group relative to the other Mesothelae described from mid-Cretaceous Burmese amber by Wunderlich (families Cretaceotheidae Wunderlich, 2015, Burmathelidae Wunderlich, 2017, and Parvithelidae Wunderlich 2017).

Another argument that could support a splitting of Liphistiidae s. lat. into separate families would be that a very deep and ancient split separates the two major lineages. Quite the opposite is the case: the radiation of Liphistiidae s. lat. in Southeast Asia is a surprisingly recent event that was initially completely unexpected for such an ancient and conservative lineage (Xu et al. 2015b). The split between the Liphistiinae and Heptathelinae has been variously dated to between 48 million years ago (Mya; 95% credibility interval 39–58 Mya; Xu et al. 2015) and 102 Mya (95% CI 92–113 Mya; Xu et al. 2021). This indicates that Liphistiidae s. lat. are a *younger* family than many other well-delimited and widely accepted spider families. For example, crown group Oonopidae, Tetrablemmidae and Pacullidae are reported from mid-Cretaceous Burmese amber, dated 98.79 Mya (Magalhaes et al. 2020, Xin et al. 2021), as are Psilodercidae (Magalhaes et al. 2021); in contrast, Liphistiinae and Heptathelinae are absent from Burmese amber, which contains a diverse range of other mesothelid fossils (Wunderlich 2017). The divergence within both Araneidae and Theridiidae is consistently dated to more than 100 Mya in various analyses (Magalhaes et al. 2020, Dimitrov et al. 2017, Kallal et al. 2020, Scharff et al. 2022); the earliest fossil member of Palpimanidae has been reported from 115–120 Mya (Downen & Selden 2021); Theraphosidae

have an estimated divergence time of 119 Mya (Foley 2021), with fossils known from Burmese amber (Wunderlich & Müller 2020); the most recent common ancestor of Linyphiidae has been dated to 129 Mya (95% HPD 125–136 Mya; Tian et al. 2022); and Archoleptonetidae (112 Mya) and Leptonetidae (126 Mya) are both molecularly dated as being of Cretaceous origin (Ledford et al. 2021), while for Filistatidae an even more extreme age of 182–187 Mya has been estimated (Magalhaes & Ramírez 2022). Crown-group Liphistiidae s. lat. is thus younger than many other spider families across the spider tree of life. This recent rapid, local diversification of Liphistiidae s. lat., in striking contrast to its overall appearance as a homogeneous and static group of “living fossils”, is the most compelling evolutionary feature of the group. Splitting the homogeneous family into two would largely obscure this curious and important fact.

The very recent split between Liphistiinae and Heptathelinae, happening no earlier than the mid-Cretaceous, also supports the earlier hypothesis that the two subfamilies form a monophyletic group, relative to the diverse assemblage of other Mesothelae reported from mid-Cretaceous amber. By splitting the recent Mesothelae into two separate families this important phylogenetic hypothesis would no longer be explicit in the classification, reducing its overall information content.

On the other hand, the diversification *within* each of the two subfamilies is even more strikingly recent. The initial divergence within Liphistiinae (genus *Liphistius*) is dated to between 17 Mya (95% CI 11–24 Mya; Xu et al. 2015b) and 28 Mya (95% CI 25–31 Mya), while that within Heptathelinae (the split between the mainland and insular clade) is dated to between 33 Mya (95% CI 28–39 Mya; Xu et al. 2015b) and 39 Mya (95% CI 35–44 Mya; Xu et al. 2021). Many well-defined and rather homogeneous *genera* of extant spiders, across the spider tree of life, are older than these two subfamilies. For example, *Stedocys* (Scytodidae) began its initial divergence 55 Mya (95% CI 44–67 Mya; Luo & Li 2018); *Arctosa* (Lycosidae) diversified 32–40 Mya (Piacentini & Ramírez 2019); the morphologically very uniform genus *Antrodiaetus* (Antrodiaetidae) diversified about

115 Mya (highest posterior density 59–178 Mya; Hedin et al. 2019); *Zodarion* (Zodariidae) diversified at the Cretaceous/Paleogene boundary, 65 Mya (95% CI 40–98 Mya; Ortiz et al. 2022); *Dysdera* (Dysderidae) diversified since 47.1 Mya (Crespo et al. 2021); *Micrathena* (Araneidae) about 58 Mya (CI 33–71 Mya; Shapiro et al. 2022); *Caribena* (Theraphosidae) 41.5 Mya (Foley 2021); *Sicarius* (Sicariidae) 55.6 Mya (HPD 34.2–80.7; Magalhaes et al. 2019). Even though all the individual estimates are associated with considerable uncertainty, collectively they strongly agree that raising the Liphistiinae and Heptathelinae to family rank would represent a serious oversplitting, in particular when evaluating the molecular dating in the context of the overall morphological, ecological and behavioural homogeneity of the Liphistiidae s. lat. In fact, one could argue with greater conviction in favour of downgrading the two subfamilies to genus rank, with the genera within Heptathelinae being considered mere subgenera of *Heptathela* s. lat.

In conclusion, raising the subfamilies of Liphistiidae s. lat., the extant primitively segmented spiders, to family rank is not justified. Doing so would obscure the most important evolutionary features of this group: their monophyly relative to the diversity of mid-Cretaceous and earlier Mesothelae, and their very recent local radiation in contrast to their status as “living fossils”. I therefore reject the proposal of Li (2022) and propose to maintain a single family Liphistiidae s. lat. for all recent Mesothelae.

Acknowledgements

I thank Paul Selden and two anonymous reviewers for their helpful comments on an earlier version of this manuscript.

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Published online: 1 October 2022

Pierre Bonnet and the Clerckian legacy: an arachnohistorical anniversary

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Abstract. Seventy-five years ago, Pierre Bonnet issued a petition to the Commission for Zoological Nomenclature, requesting that action be taken to ensure the availability of Carl Clerck's widely used names for some of Europe's most common spiders, despite their publication before the official starting point of zoological nomenclature. His efforts were successful, and the Clerckian names have since been used consistently. This article reviews the history of the case and its implications for the correct dating of Clerck's work: its actual publication date is established to be Monday, 18 April 1757.

The most recent checklists of European spiders list 53 valid species attributed to “Clerck, 1757”, including some of the most common, notable and widespread species in the region, such as *Araneus diadematus*, *Salticus scenicus*, *Zygiella x-notata*, *Linyphia triangularis*, *Metellina segmentata*, *Pardosa amentata*, *Pisaura mirabilis*, *Enoplognatha ovata*, *Philodromus aureolus* and *Xysticus cristatus*, as well as *Araneus angulatus* Clerck, 1757, the very first officially named animal species. All of these names were first published in Carl Clerck's exemplary treatise on Swedish Spiders (*Svenska Spindlar/Aranei Svecici*), published in Swedish with a parallel Latin translation in Stockholm in 1757 (Clerck 1757; see Kronstedt 2010 and Walter 2007 for discussions of the historical context of the work).

It is all but forgotten that there was a time, not too long ago, when we were close to losing Clerck's names to a quirk of the rules of zoological nomenclature, as having been published before the official starting point of zoological nomenclature, taken to be the publication date of the tenth (expanded) edition of Carl Linnaeus's *Systema Naturae* in 1758 (Anonymous 1893b: Art. 45 and subsequent versions of the international rules of zoological nomenclature). For several decades of confusion, alternative names like *Aranea diadema*, *Zygiella litterata*, *Pisaura listeri*, *Lycosa saccata*, *Xysticus*

viaticus or *Theridion redimitum* were regularly used for some of the common spiders named by Clerck. Some readers may still remember them, e.g., from Bristowe's *Comity of Spiders* (1939/41) or the early volumes of *Die Tierwelt Deutschlands* (e.g., Dahl 1926, Wiehle 1931). At some point it even seemed as if there was a good chance that this rather messy situation would never be resolved.

Bonnet's *Pétition* of 1947 and the challenge of its implementation

That it didn't come to this is due to the heroic initiative of a single spider taxonomist, the French arachnologist Pierre Bonnet. In 2022, we celebrate the 75th anniversary of Bonnet's *Pétition adressée à la Commission de Nomenclature zoologique en faveur de la priorité des noms d'Araignées de Clerck* (Bonnet 1947; **Figure 1**). In this privately published pamphlet of 26 pages, Bonnet argued that Clerck's work is such a superior work of arachnological scholarship, compared to Linnaeus's subsequent treatment in the *Systema Naturae* of 1758, and his names so widely used by eminent arachnologists throughout history and around the globe, that an insistence by the *Commission* on rejecting the Clerckian names would be met with widespread resistance and nomenclatural anarchy. He supports his argument with detailed statistics, outlined in numerous tables based on the most comprehensive review of the araneological literature. Bonnet shared this petition with 62 leading arachnologists from around the world, asking for their views on the issue. Out of 54 respondents, 48 voted in favour of his proposal, with only 4 raising objections, the other 2 abstaining (Bonnet 1950).

The case was then discussed in three meetings of the *Commission* on 22, 24 and 26 July 1948 in Paris. The rich statistical data, careful reasoning and broad international support of Bonnet's petition put the *Commission* in a difficult position. There seems to have been quick agreement that his suggestions were well justified – but how could they be implemented in the rules without causing collateral damage to other aspects of nomenclatural stability?

It was clear that it would not be acceptable to change the long-establishing starting point of zoological nomenclature. This had been

Figure 1. Title page of Bonnet's 1947 petition to the *Commission*, which resulted in the availability of the Clerckian names, despite their actual publication before the start date of zoological nomenclature.

arbitrarily fixed in 1892, after extensive and lively debates, as the year 1758, the year the zoological section of the 10th edition of Linnaeus's *Systema Naturae* had been published (Anonymous 1893a, Blanchard 1893, Bonnet 1947). Changing it would have potential consequences not just for spider nomenclature, but also for that of other groups for which researchers had introduced binomial names well before Linnaeus (such as molluscs). This provision gave priority to Linnaeus's names over any other scientific names published the same year, and denied availability to any names published before 1758, such as the Clerckian names (in cases where such early names had been re-used by Linnaeus they were attributed to him as author).

But it was also considered inappropriate by the *Commission* members to assign a counterfactual publication date of 1758 to Clerck's *Svenska spindlar*, when it was undeniable that it had been published in 1757, well before Linnaeus's book, which relied heavily on Clerck's work in its short arachnological section. That the 1757 publication date was not disputed by the *Commission* is clear from the records of its debates and decisions, which

consistently refer to publication of Clerck's book in 1757 (e.g., Anonymous 1950b, 1950c, 1959).

Finally, it was seen as undesirable (and logically inconsistent) to have multiple alternative starting points for zoological nomenclature, depending on which work or which taxonomic group was being considered; it appeared nonsensical to the *Commission* that the starting point of spider taxonomy should differ from that of other groups of animals.

So, what was there to do? In the end, the *Commission* came up with a solution of admirable clarity and elegance: on Monday, 26 July 1948, in a meeting held at the Sorbonne in the Amphitheatre Louis-Liard, at 1445 hours "The *Commission* agreed to recommend: ...that a proviso should be added to Article 26 [of the *Règles internationales de la nomenclature zoologique*] directing that, notwithstanding the general provisions of that Article, the generic name *Araneus* and the specific trivial names for species of the Class Arachnida published in 1757 [sic] in Clerck's *Aranei svecici* are to be treated as though they had been published subsequent to the starting point of zoological nomenclature and are to have priority as though they had been published in the year 1758 on some date prior to the publication of the 10th edition of Linnaeus's *Systema Naturae*" (Anonymous 1950b). Thus, instead of changing the starting point of zoological nomenclature, this decision establishes a *legal fiction*, more specifically, a "deeming provision" (indicated by the repeated phrase "as though") – changing the application of the rules, without having to alter or ignore the historical facts.

When, during a revision of the rules in preparation of the first *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature*, which was to replace the *Règles* in 1961 (Anonymous 1961), this provision was accidentally removed, it was reinstated with slightly altered wording by Direction 104 of the *Commission*, published in 1959, which ruled under the title "Grant of the status of availability to the names published by C. A. Clerck in 1757 [sic] in the work *Aranei Svecici*..." that "the generic name *Araneus* (Class Arachnida) and the specific names published in combination with it in C. A. Clerck's *Aranei svecici* are hereby ruled to be available as though they had been published subsequent to the starting

point of zoological nomenclature and are to have priority as though they had been published in 1758 prior to the publication of the 10th edition of Linnaeus's *Systema Naturae*" (Anonymous 1959). Again, the repeated phrase "as though" clarifies the technical status of this ruling as a deeming provision.

During the preparation of the 3rd edition of the *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature* (Anonymous 1985:7) it was decided to include the *Commission's* earlier provisions regarding the Clerckian names as an integral part of the *Code*, in a slightly more compact form, but without any change in substance: "Two works are deemed to have been published on that date [i.e., 1 January 1758]:

- Linnaeus's *Systema Naturae*, 10th Edition;
- Clerck's *Aranei Svecici*.

Names in the latter have precedence over names in the former..." (Art. 3)

This short sentence again emphasises that the publication date for both of these works is a legal fiction, this time making it explicitly clear that we are dealing with a deeming provision in the technical legal sense ("are deemed"). The preceding debate provides further evidence that the *Commission* did not intend to change the way Clerck's work would be cited, by establishing a counterfactual publication date: at the start of the discussions, Melville (1978:78) had proposed an amendment of the *Code* requiring that "the author and date of those [Clerckian] names, if cited, must be cited as 'Clerck, [1758]'". This suggestion was later dropped without further documented discussion, and the proposal put to vote in 1980 returns to citing "Clerck, 1757" (Melville 1980:212).

The text of the 3rd edition remained essentially unchanged in the 4th edition of the *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature* (Anonymous 1999, hereafter cited as *Code*). This was prepared under the guidance of the arachnologist Otto Kraus, who had also been a member of the *Commission* during the preparation of the 3rd edition. In the form included in the 4th edition, now as Article 3.1 of the *Code*, the rule remains valid today.

A lingering confusion: Clerck, 1757 or 1758?

Nevertheless, despite its enormous practical impact for the stability and uniformity of spider

nomenclature, especially in the Palaearctic, Bonnet's efforts are rarely remembered, and his *Pétition* is one of the very few taxonomically relevant publications that are discussed on the pages of the World Spider Catalog (WSC 2022) but are missing from its comprehensive full-text collection of the arachnological literature.

Moreover, despite the rapid acceptance of Bonnet's requests by the *Commission*, some confusion has remained regarding their practical implementation: taxonomists' discussion groups on the internet contain numerous heated debates about the correct publication date of Clerck's work – should the Clerckian names be attributed to "Clerck, 1757", according to the actual publication date, or to "Clerck, 1758", as supposedly required by the *Code* (Kronestedt 2010)? Even the authors of the World Spider Catalog appear baffled by this issue and propose two alternative publication dates, 1 January 1758 and 31 December 1757, in a bewildered and bewildering discussion of the case on the catalogue's Frequently Asked Questions page (Anonymous n.d.)

What better way to celebrate the anniversary of Bonnet's successful campaign than to resolve the remaining issues and establish the precise date of publication of Clerck's spider book?

To determine this date, and to fully appreciate the genius of the *Commission* when choosing the exact wording of Article 3.1, it is first necessary to understand that there are three different publication dates associated with each scientific name – ideally all three of these dates are identical, but this is not necessarily the case.

1. Imprint date: This is the date printed as part of the original publication, typically on the title page of historical books. This date is often vague, only indicating the month or year of publication. It may also be wrong, with the actual publication happening earlier or later than indicated by the imprint date. Sometimes the date also uses a non-standard calendar, as is the case in many classic works of arachnology, which are dated according to the French revolutionary calendar. In these cases, the corresponding year of publication according to the Gregorian calendar cannot always be determined unambiguously. In the case of Clerck's *Svenska*

Figure 2. Title page of Clerck's *Svenska spindlar*, showing the imprint date MDCCLVII, i.e., 1757.

spindlar the imprint date is 1757 (**Figure 2**).

2. Date for availability and priority: This is the date most important for the practical application of the *Code*. This date can be fictitious; e.g., if only the month or year of publication is known, publication on the last day of the period is assumed (*Code* Art. 21.3); i.e., publications for which the exact day of publication is known would take precedence in terms of priority. Another example of a fictitious date for purposes of priority is the choice of 1 January 1758 as the publication date of Linnaeus's *Systema Naturae Editio Decima*: it is exceedingly unlikely that any book would have been published on New Year's Day, especially as it fell on a Sunday in 1758. Moreover, Linnaeus's book had continuously increased in size since its first 11-page edition in 1735, and by the 10th edition it was necessary to distribute the content across three volumes, of which only the first one (on zoological nomenclature) was published in 1758. The second part, on botanical nomenclature, appeared only in 1759; the third, on minerals, remains unpublished as a manuscript in the Linnean Society's collection in London. Nevertheless, establishing this legal fiction (or, more specifically, this "deeming provision"; Stern 2015:169 et passim)

guaranteed that Linnaeus's work would have priority over any other work published the same year. Such deeming provisions are usually limited in scope; in this case, it is created specifically for the purposes of availability and priority, rather than, e.g., bibliography or historiography. For Clerck's work, the publication date for availability is also 1 January 1758 (*Code* Art 3.1); in this context, treating the work as having been published on the previous day, 31 December 1757, or earlier would make the Clerckian names unavailable. For the purpose of priority, the exact time of publication is even more specific: publication is taken to have happened *before* the publication of the *Systema Naturae* and any other publication in 1758.

3. Actual date of publication: This is the date to be cited with a scientific name (together with the author's name); where they differ, the imprint date can be added in brackets (*Code* Art. 22, Recommendation 22A). That the actual, rather than any "deemed" date takes precedent when citing a taxon name is further supported by the way the *Code* treats an analogous case in the family group (*Code* Art. 40.2 Recommendation 40A). The *Code* does not allow an exception to this principle in the case of Clerck's work. In particular, the *Code* does not include any suggestion that the Clerckian taxa should be cited with their authorship given as "Clerck, 1758" as is sometimes erroneously claimed. If one wants to specifically emphasise the date for priority and availability, this would need to be added in brackets, as is done by the *Commission* in its Direction 104 (Anonymous 1959). Such an addition would be optional, and in the case of Clerck's work, it would hardly ever serve a useful purpose. The accidental omission of the mandatory brackets in the *Commission's* Opinion 2224 (Anonymous 2009) probably contributed to the confusion, but does not change the requirements of the *Code*. Thus, the *actual*, historically and bibliographically relevant, publication date is the date we need to establish for Clerck's book.

The actual publication date of Clerck's *Svenska spindlar*

It should be clear from the preceding discussion that the actual date of publication cannot be 1 January 1758: a deeming provision

or other legal fiction only changes the application of a law or regulation; it does not change the facts. In ecclesiastical law, rabbits were deemed fish for the purpose of fasting rules – but even the most pious monk would not raise his conies in an aquarium. Equally, the deeming provision established in Art. 3.1 of the *Code* does not change the actual publication date. The fictitious nature of the “1758” date is clearly emphasised in the Commission’s decisions published in 1950 and 1959, as well as in the wording of Art. 3.1. The 1959 ruling adds the title of Clerck’s work to the list of accepted works, with a publication date of “[1758]”, where the square brackets indicate that this is the deemed date for availability and priority, rather than the actual publication date (Anonymous 1959). This interpretation is confirmed by Otto Kraus (in his 1975 translation of Mayr’s *Principles of Systematic Zoology*; Mayr

1975:287), who glosses this bibliographic entry as follows: “Hier hat die Internationale Kommission verfügt, daß folgendes Werk, obgleich prae-linnaeisch, nomenklatorisch verfügbar ist [als ob von 1758]: Clerck, C. (1757)...”, thus “Here, the International Commission has decreed that the following work, despite being pre-Linnean, is available for the purposes of nomenclature [as if published in 1758]: Clerck, C. (1757)...” (emphases mine). Note, again, the telltale square brackets in the original text. Given that Kraus was not only a personal friend of Bonnet, through his organisation of the international Congresses of Arachnology, but also the main organiser of the preparation of the current version of the *Code*, his interpretation in this matter can probably be taken as authoritative.

But an actual publication date of

Figure 3. Extracts from Clerck’s letter to Linnaeus, showing his signature and the date 21 Ap[ril] 1757 (top), as well as the beginning of the postscript reporting the submission of his *Svenska spindlar* to the King, the Crown Prince and several of their courtiers on the preceding Monday (bottom) (reproduced with Permission of the Linnean Society of London).

31 December 1757 would equally be incorrect. The pages of the World Spider Catalog state that “[f]ollowing Article 21.3.2 [of the *Code*] Clerck’s book and species have been published on Dec. 31, 1757” (Anonymous n.d.). This is a common misunderstanding (previously shared even by the current Chair of the Code Editorial Committee; Welter-Schultes 2009). However, while Article 21.3.2 determines that “[the date to be adopted is] the last day of the year when only the year is specified or demonstrated”, this rule would only apply in the absence of evidence for the existence as a published work at an earlier date. In the case of *Svenska spindlar*, we have abundant evidence of its exact publication date. This evidence has been publicly available in printed form for more than a century (e.g., Fries 1911:270), and scanned versions of the originals have been available online since the Linnaeus tercentenary in 2007 (Shaughnessy 2007:4), as has been a digitised version of the transcripts by Fries (1911; available online at <https://archive.org/details/brefochskrifvels05u pps>).

Most importantly, in the collection of Carl Linnaeus’s correspondence in the Linnean Society collection in London, we find a letter by Clerck, dated 21 April 1757, where in a postscript Clerck announces that he had submitted copies of his “spindel historia”, i.e., *Svenska spindlar*, to both the King of Sweden, Adolph Frederick, to whom the book was dedicated, and the 7-year-old crown prince, the future King Gustav III *the previous Monday* (“I förleden Måndags”) (**Figure 3**; available online at <https://www.alvin-portal.org/alvin/view.jsf?pid=alvin-record%3A226576>). Additional copies were handed on the same day to the crown prince’s two governors, Carl Gustav Tessin and Carl Scheffer (Barton 1972), as well as to Abraham Bäck. These were highly educated men and regular correspondents of Linnaeus (the second edition of the *Systema Naturae* had been dedicated to Tessin; Linnaeus 1740); they represent the scientific community of the country. Clerck promises to send additional copies to Linnaeus and the Royal Society in Uppsala, as well as 12 copies for students in need (“fattiga studerandes”). In a hastily added addition to the postscript, he indicates that due to the generosity of the postmaster he is able to

include Linnaeus’s copy already with the letter, and the very next day, 22 April 1757, Linnaeus confirms the receipt of the “most beautiful” (“wackraste”) book by return mail. “I will keep your work as a sacred treasure, and it shall illuminate my dark museum” (“Edert wärk skall jag bewara som en heligdom och det skall uplysa mitt mörka museum”), he writes enthusiastically, at the same time confirming the correct dating of Clerck’s letter the previous day. The original of Linnaeus’s letter has been lost, but a contemporary copy remains in the Bergius collection of the Kungliga Svenska Vetenskapsakademien, Stockholm (available online at <https://www.alvin-portal.org/alvin/view.jsf?pid=alvin-record%3A226557>).

The Gregorian calendar was introduced in Sweden on 17 February 1753 (Wahlgren 2012:5). The Monday preceding 21 April 1757 would thus have been **18 April 1757**, and this date, when the work was first widely circulated in the scientific community and submitted to the Royal library, is to be taken as the actual publication date of Clerck’s *Svenska spindlar*.

Concluding reflections

Bonnet was certainly not always an easy person to work with (Anonymous 1992); his enthusiasm and critical spirit ruffled some feathers in the community, and at least one of his late papers, “Les dernières réflexions d’un arachnologiste” presented at the IVth International Congress of Arachnology in 1968 (Bonnet 1970), could only be published with a “trigger warning” by the editor, for what could be seen as its “ton excessif”. Yet, his 1947 petition and survey had enormous beneficial impact: not only did they rescue and stabilise the Clerckian names for our most common spiders, they also served as an important “community building” exercise for the arachnological world, well before the first International Congress of Arachnology.

Two years after a devastating world war that had put Bonnet’s life work, his monumental catalogue, the *Bibliographia Araneorum*, at considerable risk, such a global effort across national and political boundaries cannot have been easy, both logistically and emotionally. One just has to remember that Bonnet’s survey was addressed not only to arachnologists on both

sides of the Iron Curtain, but it included even prominent Nazi profiteers, such as Carl Roewer (who in 1933, after Hitler's rise to power, had taken over the Bremen colonial museum to streamline its exhibits according to the requirements of the "new times") and Hermann Wiehle (senior author of a notorious multi-volume biology textbook promoting Nazi racial theories to middle school students). One of the recipients of Bonnet's petition, Count Lodovico di Caporiacco, a committed fascist and early supporter of Mussolini already in the 1920s, was even a member of the *Commission* and was asked to introduce the case to his fellow members at the 1948 Paris meetings. This historical background makes Bonnet's achievements even more impressive.

So, in the future, whenever we cite *Araneus diadematus* Clerck, 1757, or any of the other familiar spider names introduced by Clerck in his magnum opus, let us also gratefully remember Pierre Bonnet, whose determination and resolve have conserved these names for posterity.

Acknowledgements

I thank Michael Schmitt (Greifswald) and Francisco W. Welter-Schultes (International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature) for their very constructive comments on an earlier version of the manuscript, which have helped clarifying the argument. Tobias Bauer, Theo Blick, Petr Dolejš and Konrad Wiśniewski provided additional helpful suggestions.

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Published online: 1 October 2022

On the identity of *Aranea subterranea* Roemer, 1789, type species of the genus *Atypus* (Arachnida : Araneae)

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Abstract. The identity of *Aranea subterranea* Roemer, 1789, the type species of the genus *Atypus* Latreille, 1804, has recently come under some suspicion. Here, the evidence regarding the case is reviewed and a lectotype is designated for *Aranea subterranea* and several of its synonyms, based on an illustrated specimen, to stabilise the currently accepted interpretation of *A. subterranea* as a junior synonym of *Atypus piceus* (Sulzer, 1776).

When Latreille (1804a:133) first created the genus *Atypus*, he included only a single species: *Aranea subterranea* Roemer, 1789. This species is consequently the type species of the genus by monotypy, and its correct identification becomes potentially relevant. Roemer's name was recently discussed in some detail by Sherwood (2021), but unfortunately the brief argument, a mere aside in a larger text dealing with other topics, includes a number of misunderstandings and mistranslations of the earlier literature. As a result, some uncertainty arises regarding the correct identification of the species involved, which potentially could create unnecessary confusion for later taxonomists. It is therefore worthwhile having a closer look at the case to clarify the identity and nomenclatorial status of *Aranea subterranea* Roemer, 1789.

Sherwood's text is very concise and can be cited here in full, as a starting point for the discussion: “**1** Roemer (1789) described *Aranea subterranea* Roemer, 1789[,] and the description (minus the habitat which was erroneously described as aquatic) and the plate both clearly indicate this as a mygalomorph spider. **2** Latreille (1804[b]) noted that the habitat information from Roemer (1789) was doubtful, hence Roemer instead naming the taxon *Aranea subterranea*. **3** In the same work, Latreille (1804[b]) considers new material he examined as conspecific with Roemer's taxon[,] but [this] is instead considered *A. affinis* by

Bonnet (1955: 397). **4** Some years later, Simon (1873) placed *A. subterranea* Roemer, 1789 in synonymy with *Atypus piceus* (Sulzer, 1776) where it has remained since (World Spider Catalog 2021). **5** This synonymy was well supported and has been accepted by later workers (e.g. Gertsch 1936, Perkovsky et al. 2018).” (Sherwood 2021:8; sentences numbered for reference below)

This initially seems to be an entirely reasonable presentation of the case. However, as shown below, a closer look at the argument reveals that, rather surprisingly, every single sentence of this text contains questionable statements. Naturally, this gives reason to question whether the currently accepted interpretation of the identity of the species is indeed correct.

1. Roemer (1789:66; **Figure 1**) does *not* provide any description of *Aranea subterranea* at all, and the only (entirely correct!) information given concerns the habitat of the new species, which is “nonnisi in subterraneis reperitur”, i.e. “only found below ground”, rather than being aquatic. Instead of giving a description of *A. subterranea*, Roemer quotes the description and habitat information of *Aranea aquatica* (!) from Fabricius (“Fusca, abdomine ovato cinereo: dorso fusco punctis duobus impressis. Habitat in Europae aquis dulcibus”; Fabricius 1775:436), and then states that his own species (“nostra”, which is illustrated in Tab. XXX, f. 2) “omnino ad *aquaticae* Fabr. descriptionem quadret”, i.e., it “entirely squares with Fabricius's description of *A. aquatica*”; however, because of the different habitat “hinc potius *subterranea* nuncupanda”, “thus [his species] should probably rather be called *subterranea*”. The confident identification of Roemer's species is possible only because of the accompanying illustration, which indeed shows a mygalomorph spider, not *Aranea aquatica* (i.e., *Argyroneta aquatica* (Clerck, 1757)). The name *Aranea subterranea* is thus originally published as a (doubtful) junior synonym of *A. aquatica*, and the conditions of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN 2012) Article 11.6 (“Publication as a synonym”) apply: “A name which when first published in an available work was treated as a junior synonym of a name then used as valid is not thereby made

Aquatica. FABR. S. Ent. n. 22 ?

Fusca, abdomine ovato cinereo: dorso fusco, punctis duobus impressis.

Tab. XXX. f. 2. Habitat in Europæ aquis dulcibus. FABR. at nostra, quamvis omnino ad *aquaticæ* Fabr. descriptionem quadret, tamen nonnisi in subterraneis reperitur, hinc potius *subterranea* nuncupanda ?

Figure 1. The original text in Roemer (1789) establishing the name *Aranea subterranea*.

available.” It is also clear that Roemer does not describe a new species *A. aquatica*, despite Roewer’s (1942) claim to the contrary (and the subsequent mistaken entry in the World Spider Catalogue).

2. Latreille (1804b:168) does not express any doubt about the habitat information provided by Roemer; quite the contrary is the case: he fully accepts the statement that the species is “subterranean” and thus maintains Roemer’s name, removing it formally from the synonymy with *A. aquatica*, and as a result making the name available according to ICZN Art. 11.6.1 (“However, if such a name published as a junior synonym had been treated before 1961 as an available name and either adopted as the name of a taxon or treated as a senior homonym, it is made available...”). Latreille simply states that Roemer had suspected a potential synonymy of his species with *Aranea aquatica* as described by Fabricius, but that he had expressed doubts about this identification and thus had proposed the new name *A. subterranea*.

3. Latreille (1804b), and his colleague Walckenaer (1805), indeed considered their material of *Atypus* from the Paris region to be conspecific with Roemer’s species. This was first doubted by Simon (1914), who on the basis of

relative frequency considered it more likely that Latreille’s (and Walckenaer’s) material was *A. affinis* Eichwald, 1830. Bonnet follows Simon’s assessment, but not entirely consistently, as we will see below.

4. The synonymy of *A. subterranea* and *A. picea* Sulzer, 1776 was already known to Latreille (1804b:168; 1806:85) and Walckenaer (1805:7; 1806:6), and is clearly stated by both of them, even when they introduce their own alternative names for the same species (*Oletera atypus* Walckenaer, 1805; *Atypus sulzeri* Latreille, 1806).

5. None of the cited authors discusses the reasons for the synonymy or provides any arguments in its favour. It is, thus, unclear what would justify the statement that the synonymy “was well supported”. At first glance, as the type material is lost and the descriptions are far too vague to allow a confident identification at the species level, finding the necessary support would seem a rather hopeless case.

However, the situation is much more interesting than this: as explained above, the only usable diagnostic information about the habitus of *Aranea subterranea* is provided by the accompanying figure (**Figure 2**). Interestingly, this is the exact same figure as that of Tab. XXX, fig. 2 accompanying Sulzer’s description of

Figure 2. Top part of the identical Tab. XXX in Roemer (1789) and Sulzer (1776), showing *Aranea picea* / *Aranea subterranea* on the right.

Aranea picea (Sulzer 1776:254). The figures are not just very similar, but identical, in all probability printed from the same copper plate: the two works were published by the same publishing house in Winterthur, and it was common practice of the time to re-use the valuable plates of illustrated works to maximize economic profit. In fact, the specimen illustrated by Sulzer is the only member of the original type series of *Aranea subterranea* for which we have more than the most superficial information. Apparently, this identity of the illustrations was already noted in passing by Simon (1914), who in his chresonymy of *Atypus piceus* (Sulzer) adds that Roemer's work includes "ead. fig." ("eadem figura", the same figure). However, he does not further discuss the implications of this observation.

An analogous case is seen for *Oletera atypus* Walckenaer, 1805 and *Atypus sulzeri* Latreille, 1806 – both of them include Sulzer's (and Roemer's) specimen in their type series (by "bibliographic reference"; ICZN Art. 72.4 "Type series"), and no other material from the type series is documented.

Given that all type material is lost (Kraus & Baur 1974:86), I here designate the (lost) specimen used for the illustration in Tab. XXX, fig. 2 in Sulzer (1776) and Roemer (1789) as the **lectotype** of *Aranea picea* Sulzer, 1776, *Aranea subterranea* Roemer, 1789, *Oletera atypus* Walckenaer, 1805 and *Atypus sulzeri* Latreille, 1806, according to ICZN Art. 74.4 ("Designation by means of an illustration or description": "the fact that the specimen no longer exists or cannot be traced does not of itself invalidate the designation"). The four names thus become objective synonyms, with *Aranea picea* Sulzer, 1776 taking priority.

In the case of *Atypus sulzeri*, it is clear from the choice of epithet that Latreille intended this synonymy when introducing the new name. In the older literature, one sometimes sees this kind of unnecessary replacement name proposed for a name that an author felt to be "inappropriate", e.g., for not properly emphasising the relevant diagnostic characters, but this does not seem to apply here. Thus, it remains a mystery why Roemer, Walckenaer and Latreille each felt the need to introduce a new name for the same species, even though they

were in each case evidently aware of *all* their predecessors, including Sulzer (1776).

The synonymy of *A. subterranea* with *A. picea* was also recognized by Bonnet (1955), when he stated that the type species of the genus *Atypus* Latreille, 1804 is *Atypus piceus* (Sulzer, 1776). This is, however, not entirely consistent with his assumption that Latreille had misidentified the species and had actually based the new genus on specimens of what later became known as *Atypus affinis* (Eichwald, 1830).

In this case, the regulations of ICZN Article 70 ("Identification of the type species") apply. In particular, "[i]t is to be assumed, in the absence of clear evidence to the contrary, that an author has identified the species correctly when he or she [...] includes a previously established nominal species in a new nominal genus..." As there is no clear evidence to support Simon's and Bonnet's merely probabilistic hypothesis that Latreille had misidentified his type species, we thus have to assume that the type species is indeed *Aranea subterranea* Roemer, i.e., *Atypus piceus* (Sulzer), as is generally accepted in the literature (e.g., Kraus & Baur 1974, Gertsch & Platnick 1980, Schwendinger 1990, Perkovsky et al. 2018). The designation of a lectotype further stabilises the situation, and also eliminates potential confusion regarding a possible priority of *Oletera atypus* Walckenaer, 1805 and *Atypus sulzeri* Latreille, 1806 over *A. affinis* Eichwald, 1830, thus addressing the concerns expressed by Bonnet (1955) in this regard.

Acknowledgements

I thank Tobias Bauer, Petr Dolejš and two anonymous reviewers for their helpful comments on an earlier version of this manuscript.

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Published online: 1 October 2022

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ISSN 2753-4804

[urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:92ECF7B2-B66E-43F8-9BD2-5A9E1BC75747](https://zoobank.org/pub/92ECF7B2-B66E-43F8-9BD2-5A9E1BC75747)

Publication date: 1 October 2022